

TABLE 2—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF THE LIGANDS AND COMPLEXES

Temp. = 30 ± 0.1°, $\mu = 0.1 M$

Cation	Ligand (A)		Ligand (B)	
	log K_1	log K_2	log K_1	log K_2
H ⁺	11.89	10.24	13.21	11.27
UO ₂ ^{II}	13.75	11.81	12.46	11.15
Cu ^{II}	12.28	10.56	12.85	11.10
Ni ^{II}	11.43	10.18	9.12	—
Co ^{II}	8.23	7.00	8.30	8.08
Zn ^{II}	11.29	9.65	10.80	—

dihydroxybenzylidene phenylhydrazone, Cu^{II}>UO₂^{II}>Ni^{II}>Zn^{II}>Co^{II}.

Schiff bases are known to have chemotherapeutic activity against tubercule bacilli and other bacteria as well as against skin fungi⁵. The thiosemicarbazone of 4-acetamidobenzaldehyde (thioacetazone)⁷ was introduced for the treatment of tuberculosis in 1950. This was the first synthesised drug that approached the activity of streptomycin in experimentally induced infections in animals⁶⁻⁸. The presence of azomethine linkage in compounds has been known to decrease the toxicity considerably^{9,10}. Hence, *in vitro* antitubercular screening of these compounds was carried out against the human virulent strain of *Mycobacterium tuberculosis* (H₃₇Rv) by the method of disperse-culture technique, using Kirchner's medium containing Tween-80 as dispersing agent. The antitubercular activity shown by 2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene thiosemicarbazone is 6.2 $\mu\text{g ml}^{-1}$, while 2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene phenylhydrazone is inactive. It is felt worthwhile to study the activity of 2,4-dihydroxybenzylidene thiosemicarbazone further, and the work is in progress.

References

1. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
2. H. A. FLASCHKA, "EDTA Titration", Pergamon, New York, 1978.
3. A. I. VOGEL, "A Text Book of Quantitative Inorganic Analysis", 3rd. ed., Longmans, London, 1961, p. 539.
4. H. M. IRVING and U. S. MAHNOT, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1968, 30, 1215.
5. A. G. SCHERING, Ger. Pat., 855 121/1952.
6. LEHMANN, *Lancet*, 1946, 1, 14.
7. A. LEWIS and R. SHEPHERD, "Medicinal Chemistry", 1970, Vol. 1, p. 428.
8. A. B. RICH and R. H. FOLLIS, *Bull. John Hopkins Hosp.*, 1938, 62, 177.
9. F. D. POPP, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1964, 7, 210.
10. F. D. POPP, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1961, 26, 1566.

Kinetics of Oxidation of α -Methylnaphthalene by Potassium Permanganate

R. GOPALAN* and K. EKAMBARAM

Madras Christian College, Tambaram, Madras-600 059

Manuscript received 2 January 1979, revised 10 April 1986, accepted 25 June 1986

THE oxidation of toluene by potassium permanganate has been extensively investigated¹. However, the oxidation of methylnaphthalene, which is a structural analogue of toluene has hitherto not been studied. In this paper we report the kinetics of oxidation of α -methylnaphthalene by permanganate in aqueous acetic acid.

Experimental

α -Methylnaphthalene (B.D.H.) was purified by fractional distillation, and collecting the fraction distilling at 240°. The other chemicals used were of AnalaR grade. The reactions were carried out at 30.0 ± 0.1° in 80% (v/v) acetic acid-water medium, unless otherwise specified. The pseudo-first order reaction was followed by quenching aliquots at definite time intervals in potassium iodide solution and titrating the liberated iodine against standard thiosulphate solution.

Product analysis : It was found that one mole of α -methylnaphthalene was required for the complete reduction of one mole of permanganate. The main product was α -naphthaldehyde. α -Naphthoic acid was formed in trace amounts (Table 1). Naphthyl alcohol, dinaphthyl and any other related

TABLE 1

Product	mole/mole KMnO ₄	M.p. (°C)	
		Found	Lit.
α -Naphthaldehyde	0.96	258	262
α -Naphthoic acid	negligible	164	161-3
2,4-Dinitrophenyl hydrazone	0.96	191	188

compounds were not detected. The products were isolated from the reaction mixture by ether extraction by following the procedure described in the oxidation of toluene by permanganate¹. The aldehyde was estimated as its 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone.

Results and Discussion

Only a trace amount of α -naphthoic acid compared to the amount of α -naphthaldehyde was obtained in the oxidation. Hence it may be concluded that the oxidation of the aldehyde proceeds at a negligible rate as compared to that of α -methylnaphthalene under the experimental conditions. This is in accordance with an earlier observation with several oxidants that side-chains attached to fused ring

systems are not easily oxidised to carboxyl groups unlike those in benzene².

The rate at which permanganate is consumed obeys first order rate laws when the substrate is in excess. Hence the order of the reaction with respect to permanganate is one (Table 2). The order with respect to substrate is also found to be one, the overall order being two. The reaction was followed at different temperatures and the activation parameters were evaluated, $\Delta H^* = 12.6 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$, $\Delta S^* = 18.2 \text{ e.u.}$, and $\Delta G^* = 18.1 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$ (30°).

TABLE 2

[S] M	[O] M	Temp. O	Solvent (v/v) AcOH-H ₂ O	$k_1 \times 10^3$ min ⁻¹
0.05	0.001	30.0	80-20	2.08
0.05	0.002	30.0	80-20	2.02
0.05	0.003	30.0	80-20	2.18
0.012	0.002	30.0	80-20	0.51
0.010	0.002	30.0	80-20	0.42
0.008	0.002	30.0	80-20	0.35
0.075	0.002	27.5	80-20	1.20
0.075	0.002	40.0	80-20	2.40
0.075	0.002	45.0	80-20	2.61
0.075	0.002	50.0	80-20	4.15
0.08	0.002	30.0	75-25	1.68
0.08	0.002	30.0	78-22	1.48
0.08	0.002	30.0	80-20	1.44
0.08	0.002	30.0	85-15	1.00

Effect of acetic acid: The effect of the solvent was investigated in the range 75–85% acetic acid; below 75% concentration the substrate is insoluble and above 85% the oxidant is insoluble. A decrease in rate constant was observed with an increase in acetic acid content of the reaction medium. The rate constants do not give a straight line for any of the Arrhenius correlations. This implies that the solvent does not directly influence the transition state. It is likely that the variation in acetic acid content of the medium alters the redox potential of the manganese-systems in such a manner that the oxidising capacity of the active oxidant is diminished. It is well established that redox potentials are sensitive to changes in medium.

Effect of Mn^{II} ions: A characteristic feature of permanganate oxidations is the possible concurrent involvement of more than one manganese species as oxidants. However, for a particular reaction, depending upon the experimental conditions, a particular manganese species may be the predominant oxidant. A diagnostic test for the predominant involvement of MnO₄⁻ over other species is the impedance in rate when Mn^{II} ions are introduced in the reaction medium. Mn^{II} ions decrease [MnO₄⁻] by reaction with the latter producing intermediate manganese ions³. In this study a sharp decrease in rate constant is noticed when manganous sulphate is added to the reaction medium (Fig. 1). This substantiates the hypothesis that MnO₄⁻ is the primary oxidant in this reaction. That the reaction

does not cease even when [Mn^{II}] is about ten times [MnO₄⁻], indicates that intermediate manganese ions are also involved—though not as predominantly as the permanganate ion—in the oxidation.

Fig. 1

Effect of pyrophosphates, fluoride and sulphate ions: These three ions influence the reaction in a similar fashion (Fig. 1). The introduction of each of these decreases the rate constant, thereby implying that besides MnO₄⁻ the reaction is effected by intermediate valence species, viz. Mn^{III} and Mn^{IV}. These anions are known to complex with active Mn^{III} and Mn^{IV} thereby obliterating their oxidising capacity⁴. However, the inability of these complexing agents to suppress the reaction completely indicates that the intermediate manganese species are not the dominant and only oxidants in this reaction.

Mechanism: A tentative mechanism may be suggested for the oxidation of α -methyl-naphthalene with MnO₄⁻ to account for the major product, α -naphthaldehyde. It may be assumed that the initial step involves the rapid formation of an intermediate, [C₁₀H₇CH₂-O-MnO₃H] consequent to a switch of electrons between the two tetrahedrally shaped reactants, C₁₀H₇-CH₃ and MnO₄⁻. This intermediate may remain trapped transiently in a solvent cage. The high negative entropy of activation (-18.2 e.u.) supports the formation of such an intermediate. This intermediate may be assumed to break down in a subsequent rate controlling step in a concerted manner yielding the aldehyde and Mn^{III} species. The Mn^{III} species thus formed may be lost due to either its involvement as an oxidant or disproportionation to Mn^{II} and Mn^{IV}⁴.

In a weakly acidic medium, MnO₄⁻ is known to abstract a hydrogen atom from the substrate form-

Scheme 1

ing a free radical intermediate². No free radical has been detected in this reaction. This observation and also the absence of products like naphthyl alcohol and dinaphthyl, which would have been formed if a free radical mechanism were operative, validate this ionic mechanism involving the direct conversation of α -methylnaphthalene to α -naphthaldehyde.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the authorities of Madras Christian College for facilities.

References

1. C. F. CULLIS and J. W. LADBURY, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 555.
2. K. B. WIBERG, "Oxidation in Organic Chemistry", Academic Press, New York, 1965, p. 1.
3. W. A. WATERS, *Quart Rev.*, 1958, 12, 281.
4. W. A. WATERS, *Quart Rev.*, 1958, 12, 296

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidation of Cycloalkanols by *N*-Chlorosaccharin

K. VIJAYA MOHAN, P. RAGHUNATHA RAO
and

E. V. SUNDARAM*

Department of Chemistry, Kakatiya University,
Warangal-506 009

Manuscript received 4 November 1985, revised 8 April 1986,
accepted 25 June 1986

THE kinetics of oxidation of alcohols by *N*-halo compounds¹⁻³ have been studied by different workers. In our earlier paper⁴ we reported the title reaction by *N*-bromosaccharin. In this paper, we present the kinetics of oxidation of cyclic alcohols by *N*-chlorosaccharin (NCSacc) in aqueous acetic acid medium with a view to find out the

nature of reactive species, ring reactivity and to propose a suitable mechanism.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade and purified further by distillation. Acetic acid (AnalaR) was refluxed over chromium trioxide. The middle fraction boiling at 117–118° (lit. 118.5°) was used. Cyclopentanol, cyclohexanol, cycloheptanol and cyclooctanol were Fluka AG samples. Oxidant was prepared by chlorination of saccharin by the usual procedure⁵. The purity of the compound is checked by tlc.

The reactions were carried out in 40% (v/v) acetic acid–water mixture at 30–50° at the desired sulphuric acid concentration (0.025–0.4 *M*). The kinetics of the reaction were followed by estimating the unreacted oxidant iodometrically⁴. All the experiments were carried out under pseudo-first order conditions using ten-fold excess of [substrate] over the [oxidant]. The stoichiometry of the reaction was determined by keeping the excess of oxidant concentration over substrate and estimating the unreacted oxidant concentration from time to time.

Results and Discussion

The stoichiometry of the reaction was found to be one mole of alcohol to one mole of oxidant as given by the equation.

The products obtained were the corresponding ketones which were identified by preparing the corresponding 2,4-DNP derivatives and comparing their melting points with the literature⁶ value. Chloride ions were identified by the usual test. When acrylonitrile was added to the reaction mixture, no polymerisation was observed indicating that the reaction did not involve free radicals as well as confirms the absence of one-electron transformation. The rate of reaction was not affected by added saccharin indicating that there was no formation of saccharin in pre-equilibrium step. This was contrary to our earlier observations on alcohol oxidation by *N*-bromosaccharin⁴. At the same time, the rate was not affected by added salts like Na₂SO₄. The order with respect to oxidant was found to be unity from the linear plots of log (*a*–*x*) vs time. However, the observed first order rate constants are slightly decreasing by increasing the oxidant concentration (Table 1). This is indicative of a prior equilibrium involving *N*-chlorosaccharin and other nucleophilic species present⁷ (probably H₂O). The observed rate constants are increasing linearly by increasing the substrate concentration in